

Pedagogical keys to inclusion and democracy in a Basque Country school: gaining knowledge from the Educational Project at Antzuola Herri Eskola

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Abstract:

The main objective of this collaborative study of a qualitative nature is to delve into the pedagogical keys of the educational project at *Antzuola Herri Eskola* (Antzuola Public School). This educational centre is a public nursery and primary school in the Basque Country with more than 40 years of innovative pedagogical experience in which the participation of students, the involvement of the educational community, as well as democratic values and well-being have become the hallmarks of the programme. In order to achieve the objective, a content analysis and information triangulation has been carried

out through the participation of three focus groups composed of the key people in charge of the project and leaders of the innovation process. Moreover, the school's own teaching publications have also been analysed, after which all of the information was arranged into different categories. The information obtained and its subsequent analysis reveal the key strategies implemented by the team of professionals at the school in promoting an inclusive and democratic educational centre that fulfils the needs of its community and current society. Furthermore, the voices of the teachers themselves demonstrate how they have implemented these key strategies into their teaching practice, and the transformations they have had to make at the curricular, organisational, and attitudinal levels.

Keywords: Democratic school, educational innovation, participation, curriculum, school organisation and school well-being.

Introduction

As pointed out decades ago by Freire (1971), an education not committed to social justice is condemned to perpetuate and reproduce existing oppression. Education goes far beyond the transmission of knowledge. Through the processes and experiences it offers, education must be committed and contribute to the development of a more egalitarian, just, and decent society. Therefore, "Schools must not merely reflect the world of which they are a part, they must be critical of it, and show in their own processes that their shortcomings are not inevitable, but can be changed" (Fielding, 2011, p. 58). These reflections have led, among other things, to extensive research in the field of democratic practices in education.

Democratic education is both an end and a means (Bolívar, 2002; Haugen, 2019; Imsen et al., 2017), because the aim is not only to educate for democracy, but also to actively

exercise this concept. This type of education is more a way of life than a set of practices to be developed within the classroom or in the realm of school organisation. In addition to the transformation of a school and its working model, the development of democratic education requires the involvement of policies that facilitate the active participation of the entire community (García-Montes, 2019; Maguire, 2018; Traver-Martí et al., 2019). To do this, the school must be capable of generating spaces where teachers, students, families and other educational participants engage in the management and development of the learning activities that take place at the school (Cousin, 2019; Dobber et al., 2012; Moliner et al., 2016; Stoll et al., 2006).

In short, democratic education requires spaces for real opportunities to exercise such education in a practical way. As such, this article affirms the need to reinforce and coordinate democratic and participatory processes that go beyond the mere representation of groups to the involvement of all members of the educational community, and to the opening of horizontal spaces for decision-making (Belavi & Murillo Torrecilla, 2016; Subirats, 2005; Trilla & Novella, 2011). Apple and Beane (1997) suggested two lines of work in order to create more democratic schools: “one is to create democratic structures and processes through which school life is shaped. The other is to create a curriculum that provides democratic experiences for young people” (p. 24). On the other hand, several authors claim that democratic practices in schools are far from being a reality (Coiduras et al., 2016; Fielding, 2004; Lodge, 2005; Mitra et al., 2013). If we examine the traditional functioning of schools, we can see that giving voice to students and their families, offering opportunities for decision-making, incorporating different participants who support the school, or guiding the teaching-learning process based on student interests, have not been common practices in the past. Moreover, a democratic school is not created through political rhetoric, but by practicing this concept every day (Apple & Beane, 1997), by

experiencing it, and by living it. For this reason, it is important to consider the beliefs held by the educational community and how they are applied to everyday life (Belavi & Murillo, 2020).

Many of the authors who have conducted research into the importance of transforming school culture in order to foster the participation of different community participants have stressed the importance of a school's management model and leadership in this process (Alvarez, 2019; Elías, 2015; Schreiber, 2019). As stated by Murillo (2006), "If we want a different society, we need different schools, and that requires a different management model as well" (p. 22). Thus, an educational community that promotes democratic participation understands that all people must have the opportunity to share ideas and knowledge in search of collective knowledge capable of generating a feeling of belonging to the school (Arguiñano, 2019; Moliner et al., 2016; Munthe & Rogne, 2015).

In spite of the current research being carried out by the scientific community regarding the ways to promote a change that will generate greater well-being in the educational community, we need practical examples to observe and analyse deeply in order to create a theory based on such practice. As stated by Escudero and Martinez (2011), "There are frequent appeals to democracy, justice and equality, but they lack the necessary struggle against the dynamics and structures that result in the violation of basic values and principles" (p. 86).

This was the approach of Fielding and Moss (2011) when they argued that if we want to make progress regarding "social alternatives" in education, it is necessary to create micro-stories by reviewing the practices of innovative, transformative educational projects. They describe these micro-stories as "critical case studies of possibilities". Despite their differences and peculiarities, such micro-stories allowed the authors to

identify common features in both processes. Thus, these projects are examples of the commitment of the community and schools with democratic educational principles organised on the basis of cooperative, democratic values, which place great importance on the pedagogy of relationships and active listening, and see knowledge as the result of a process of collective construction. Similar to the review of “critical case studies of possibilities”, Grosvenor and Pataki (2017) added common features of other examples such as the transformative vision of fighting for a better society, the importance of creativity, or the vision of students as active agents in their own learning, and the key role of the teacher in enabling this process. “The school has always run the risk of being a place of regulation and standardisation” (Fielding & Moss, 2011, p. 15), in charge of reproducing the interests of the neoliberal system and the capitalist economy. Quite to the contrary, the micro-stories or case studies such as those mentioned above remind us that schools can be something different, making an active and crucial contribution to a democratic, responsible society. The contribution being made in this sense is increasingly widespread (Arguiñano, 2019; Belavi, 2019; Garcia-Perez, 2014; Helgevold, 2016), giving visibility to examples from which we can learn. In this paper we want to elucidate another micro-story, another “critical case study of possibilities”, which will shed light on democratic education for social justice.

Antzuola Herri Eskola: a community and participatory educational project

Among the pedagogical innovation projects that have prospered in the Basque Country, the one proposed by the *Antzuola Herri Eskola* (Antzuola Public School) has attracted the attention of various authors (Arguiñano et al., 2020, 2018; Arregi, 2015; Irazabal & Mujika, 2017; Jauregui Elizondo, 2014; Karrera et al., 2019; Sasieta & Etxaniz, 2015). For more than 40 years, this public school has been immersed in a continual process of

pedagogical innovation in which the participation of students and families, as well as democratic values and the well-being of the school community, have become its hallmarks (Antzuola, 2004b; Basasoro et al., 2018). In 1980, the educational community decided to transform the pedagogical and organisational model that was dominant at the time, and to do so, they drew upon various theories and innovative experiences from that period as a reference. Next, they undertook a process of reflection in order to develop and build their own educational project adapted to the desires and needs of their community (Antzuola, 1999, 2000, 2001a, 2001b, 2003, 2004a, 2004b, 2006, 2008, 2014).

This educational model is based on a social concern for the education of its community, and the original concept has evolved along with the people who have lead the project. Therefore, the model has been growing and adapting to the needs of a community in continuous change. As a result, during all of these years they have tried to promote a respectful and welcoming environment for the educational community (Karrera et al., 2020). The curriculum at Antzuola H.E. is framed within the methodology known as Project Based Learning (PBL), where dialogue and communication with and among students is a priority. With this curriculum, there are no specific subjects. Instead, daily educational practise is focused on developing projects that are proposed, developed and shared by the students themselves by means of the democratic process, thus fulfilling the essential characteristics of PBL (Walker et al., 2015). Each work project is unique and never duplicated, as each group works according to the interests that emerge from its members. Moreover, the didactic design is not rigid, but flexible, providing the opportunity to delve into new ideas and fields of research that arise throughout the learning process. For this reason, the procedure of a project might deviate from the initial approach depending on the concerns, interests or difficulties experienced by the work group (Sasieta & Etxaniz, 2015).

The school is envisioned as a social framework in which the ideas, emotions and interpretations of reality contributed by each individual interact with each other to generate collective knowledge. The multi-faceted knowledge that emerges from this cooperation promotes an inclusive community with enhanced learning experiences.

A school must encourage a specific, special environment; a place where there is freedom to think; a place where everyone's ideas are important; where it is understood that all of us have something to learn and something to teach; a place where knowledge does not perceive hierarchies; where one opinion is no better than another, since all are hypotheses and possibilities; a place where one believes that science is relative, limited, and changing; a place where students feel they are not categorised according to their ideas (Hik Hasi, 2003, p.86).

Due to these characteristics, the Antzuola Educational Project has managed to become an important benchmark in the Basque Government's (Department of Education, Language Policy and Culture, 2016) commitment to education for the purpose of achieving an Inclusive Quality School, as well as an important centre for investigating the strategies that have made it possible to democratise the educational centre.

Materials and methods

The main objective of this study is to examine in detail the educational project at Antzuola Herri Eskola by paying special attention to the key educational strategies that sustain the programme. In order to do this, we have taken the following steps:

- Firstly, the relationship between the care and dedication towards school well-being has been analysed as one of the foundations of its pedagogical practice.

- Secondly, this study has identified the democratic procedures and pedagogical strategies for the creation of knowledge that this educational community has developed.

Latorre et al. (1996) point out that situations and relations in the community, the school, and the family can best be understood in a holistic manner. For this reason, we have chosen to design this research based on a so-called “collaborative study” (Carr & Kemmis, 1988), and as the research is qualitative, we see ourselves in a position of being able to recognise and clarify the tasks and attitudes of the people who interact daily in the programme.

In the process of gathering information, an extensive review and analysis of the documentation was carried out with regard to material published by the teaching staff of the school (articles in academic journals, books, book chapters, conference proceedings, etc.), as well as unpublished material (internal working documents, exemplary projects, communications, and other work produced for various congresses, in addition to posters and scale models made by the school’s team of professionals). Furthermore, three “Focus Groups” (Table 1) were organised to gain knowledge about “the meanings and interpretations that participating members attribute to the facts regarding the project”. In order to select the participants who took part in the Focus Groups, the following two conditions were established and agreed upon with the coordinators and administrators of the school: firstly, the people who would take part in the groups had to be direct participants in the educational change at the school; and secondly, the focus group members needed to be represented by the different groups involved in the subject matter under study in each Focus Group.

Initially, it was necessary to carry out a single Focus Group to gather information on the different questions that were established as a result of the reading and analysis of the documentation. To this end, an interview script was designed to collect information on the following six categories: (1) role of the students; (2) participatory curriculum; (3) school organisation; (4) community participation; (5) transformations and innovation carried out; (6) improvements observed. The script was offered to the coordinators and those in charge of the school for review and improvement. They gave their consent and signed the written document that informed them of the objectives of the study, the ultimate goal of the study, and the commitments made to the investigation by the members of the research team, the coordinators, those in charge of the educational centre, and the people who took part in the focus groups. Once the first Focus Group had been conducted, all the participants agreed on the need to carry out two more Focus Groups due to the volume of information received in the first session and the importance of the topics that needed to be discussed, which in some cases were only briefly mentioned due to a lack of time. Finally, participation in the three focus groups was established as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Focus Group participants

Focus group	Participants	Total participants
Focus group 1	- Family members: 2 - Nursery school coordinator - Retired teachers: 3 - Pedagogical consultant	7
Focus group 2	- Nursery school coordinator - Primary school coordinator - School Director - Retired teachers: 2 - Pedagogical consultant	6
Focus group 3	- Nursery school coordinators: 2 - Primary school coordinator - Retired teacher	4

Once the information had been collected, the content was analysed in order to obtain the results (Pérez Serrano, 2008). However, due to the appearance of emerging categories of an inductive nature, we were obliged to reconstruct the initial categorisation system, which was finally established according to the following topic groups and subcategories:

1. Democratic values, in which sub-categories such as inclusion, participation and people's well-being have been differentiated
2. School organisation and decision-making. Within this category, sub-categories have been established such as distributed leadership, as well as empowerment and families.
3. Didactics and the teaching profession
4. Transformation of the roles of student and teacher
5. Pedagogical training

However, the content analysis was considered insufficient to give meaning to the interpretations gathered, and for that reason the information obtained from the different sources was triangulated in order to observe the same situation from different perspectives. In this way, we tried to establish the necessary level of confidence in the truthfulness of the results obtained and thus comply with what Guba has defined as "truth value" (Guba, 1985, p. 153).

Acting in a coherent manner according to the information above regarding democratic practices, especially in collaborative studies, once we had analysed the information and prepared the reports, these were given to the participants for verification so they could be complemented and/or corrected in the aspects considered relevant if necessary. This allowed us to maintain a final dialogue with the participants in order to give meaning to

the information obtained and to start a process of shared reflection, as pointed out by Call-Cumming and Rosse (2019).

This shared reflection, or “reflexivity”, is closely related to the concept of positionality, which refers to the way that we, as researchers, understand our position in the world in relation to others, especially those who are involved in our research, or who might read it. Reflexivity is often issued as a call, or an important step in establishing the validity, rigour or ethical nature of the research being conducted (Call-Cumming & Rosse, 2019, p.3).

Furthermore, we have ensured that this research has been carried out with respect for the freedom and rights of all participants without excluding anyone. In other words, the well-being of the participants has been given more importance than the interests of the study.

Results

The next step was to make a written record of the results obtained from the analysis of the documentation review and the information gathered from the discussion groups¹. The description is based on the categories mentioned in the previous section.

Democratic values: inclusion, participation and people’s well-being

¹ The coding of the information was established as follows:

- The code (Ant) refers to the educational centre.
- The code (Dok) means that the information is collected from a written document, which may be internal (unpublished) or may be a teaching publication produced by the school's teaching staff.
- The code (ET) indicates a fragment of the conversations held in the focus groups.
- These codes are followed by the numbers of the documents assigned, or numbers of the focus groups carried out and identified by the research team for analysis. In addition, the codes are closed by the exact identification numbers.

Antzuola Herri Eskola embraces **these values** as their own. As stated by the participants, they have made a firm commitment to the school as being democratic, public, and that speaks *Euskaldun*, (the native, official language of the Basque Country).

In order to achieve this objective, they have seen the need for a personal as well as a collective commitment to pedagogical improvement, placing group interests above those of the individual. This is due to the firm belief that, *“In general, the school has a responsibility to its people, as a school”* (Ant_ET-2_00.34.24). Working with people involves encountering diverse ideas and perspectives, and the act of discussing such points of view helps to develop a shared vision of the way in which learning should be approached, or to discover the real purpose of education.

They understand and share the vision of **inclusion** as a positive value. *“It’s good for everyone, because it creates a high level of well-being for the student with regard to knowledge, and it allows for the establishment of communicative contexts that are characterised by generating intellectual experiences of great personal value”* (Ant_dok-4_42). As a result, they have made a commitment towards relationships based on solidarity and mutual responsibility. Furthermore, they point out that diversity is the key to developing knowledge, as it helps in the search for new paths and new ideas.

By focusing on students, they express two professional concerns: how the students learn, and how they feel. They see the need to unite these two processes, because in the event that a student does not feel well, even if he or she acquires the expected knowledge, then the student will not be in a position to fully internalise learning. Therefore, *“the student is accepted in a comprehensive way; the affective-emotional, sensory-motor, and relational-cognitive aspects are inseparable, as they manifest themselves and develop together”* (Ant_dok-3_9).

For all of the processes, they highlight the importance of showing respect and appreciation towards the child, as well as listening to them and understanding, and along these lines, the child must be viewed in a positive light, emphasising their virtues rather than their faults. Giving space to emotions is also important in this task. This vision presents learning as a dynamic process, and for Antzuola Herri Eskola, it is essential to identify with this concept in a positive way. A clear example can be found in the value and pedagogical potential of allowing mistakes to be made so that students do not feel judged. In this sense, they put great emphasis on mistakes as a learning tool, and for this reason, it is important to promote positive dialogue. Moreover, the approach to mistakes has to be done in a positive way so that everyone feels comfortable. To ensure well-being and affective-emotional security, *“We have to promote certain conditions, to have positive relationships with others, and ensure that we try to discover, reveal, and look after their desires”* (Ant_dok-3_9). Moreover, the looks we give, the way we place ourselves next to them, and the way we say things are all issues that we must be aware of, because children perceive these different ways of communicating. With these values in mind, *“The main objective of Antzuola Herri Eskola is the well-being of the students”* (Ant_ET-2_00.28.27), and this idea also extends to families and teachers. **Well-being** is closely related to knowledge, as well as the way we feel in the process of gaining knowledge. Teachers believe that knowledge can help children feel better. *“What the school does is not unrelated to what will happen to these children in the future. As professionals at Antzuola Herri Eskola, we consider that the ‘white glove’ test of quality education is what the school specifically does to allow children to have a positive relationship with knowledge, and what it does to allow the children to see themselves in a positive light, and be able to achieve a high degree of personal well-being”* (Ant_dok-4_41).

In order to foster a sense of well-being in relation to learning, they place great emphasis on personal relationships, and this refers not only to the relationships that students have with each other. This attitude also encompasses the relationship between teachers and students (Ant_ET-3_00.10.07). *“After all, the way of working is not between teachers and students. It’s a relationship between people, in which they progress together”* (Ant_ET-3_00.10.07). The child must feel understood. We have to listen and satisfy their needs, desires and wishes, taking into account the reality of each individual. They must feel valued, and feel that their contribution and opinion have value.

In the same way, they also understand that the family environment is a relevant source of information that allows access to culture. Therefore, families are also expert groups that can provide help in understanding the behaviour of students, or bring the knowledge of their professions to the school in order to work on other aspects of the projects. The inclusion of families into the school environment generates a multitude of benefits that help to improve the learning process of students. Incorporating the knowledge of families into group work has helped to improve the willingness of families and schools to cooperate with each other. *“The families are not just families. They are also experts. And being able to bring those people into the classroom is very satisfying, not only for the students, but for others as well. And the fact is, the students tell the families at the end of the project what they have done. After all, the families experience the process because the students share it at home, because their help is requested, because in the end, they are told about the whole process . . . The families also feel this satisfaction, and their willingness to participate increases”* (Ant_ET-3_00.27.44).

Another aim is to explore the diversity among students and reflect on differences, without leaving aside each person’s identity. Once certain opinions, ideas, and/or

positions on a particular topic have been clearly stated, the next goal is to make these ideas important to others. To do this, an especially positive atmosphere is promoted within the group in which harmony is guaranteed between the different visions the students possess and share. *“In this dynamic, students do not feel judged, because if there are mistakes, we reuse them to enhance the classroom dynamics – we don’t exclude them. And I believe this is an important key”* (Ant_ET-2_00.28.27).

Throughout their 40 years of pedagogical research, the teaching team has realised that the relationships they have with each other influence the professional work they carry out. Therefore, in order to strengthen friendships among the professionals and to learn on the basis of dialogue and reflection, they have established weekly time slots and spaces where they learn to listen to each other, help one another, learn together, open their classroom doors to each other, and so on. In this way, they feel protected in the innovative process and have progressed by facing their fears together.

Teachers and families have also been learning at the same time. They have placed great emphasis on learning how to interact with and talk to families, in an attempt to avoid blame and unease. Teachers understand that families also have the right to offer an opinion contrary to their own. Therefore, accepting and knowing how to manage this idea is important for moving towards a mutual objective. Sometimes the families are the ones who are worried, and in these situations, the task of teachers is to be with them, to understand them, and to guide them. As pointed out by one participant, *“If our aim is the well-being of the students, we must also take care of these other aspects”* (Ant_ET-3_00.29.39).

School organisation and decision-making: distributed leadership, empowerment and families

In terms of **school organisation**, they recognise the need to change the school model in an attempt to prioritise well-being, and point out that the steps or changes that need to be followed are revealed in daily practice. *“Regarding this issue, what is clear is that organisational decisions are made depending on needs. The organisation is not there only because it has to be there, and the school has to adapt to it.... That’s the difference”* (Ant_ET-3_00.46.45). Therefore, in this case, their efforts are directed at meeting the needs of their pedagogical project, and the formal organisation established by administration has been put on the back burner. For example, in order to make the most of the benefits offered by the didactics of the work projects, they created the figure of the coordinator. This person is freed from his or her teaching duties to help the tutors in the development of the work projects. Thus, in addition to offering support and pedagogical orientation, this professional is able to coordinate all the work projects carried out in the school. They also establish the schedule with the intention of facilitating the tutoring and orientation sessions of the work projects. For example, they schedule the Physical Education and English classes to take place one after the other. In this way, each tutor can spend nearly two mornings per week meeting with the coordinator and dedicate time to the group’s project.

Decision-making is carried out through dialogue. *“It’s not hierarchical. I mean, there is of course (school administration)... it’s assigned because it has to be, but well, for some jobs... the work has to be distributed, but it’s very horizontal”* (Ant_ET-3_00.38.37). The teaching staff has distributed the positions and responsibilities jointly, and the decisions are based largely on ability. The management team, for example, is mostly responsible for bureaucratic work and related tasks, yet the entire teaching staff makes decisions. In addition to balanced **participation** by the teachers, the other groups also participate actively in the dynamics of the school. In the case of the students, they

start making decisions from a very early age. It is considered very important for students to learn how to make decisions, and the teachers develop the necessary framework to allow students to decide. *“For us, power is about giving power. Nowadays, this is called empowerment, right? So we give them power. We don’t make the decisions. We tell them to do it their way... But of course, we make other decisions.... decisions that make all of this possible, if you know what I mean. We make decisions in order to make this framework possible. So we decide, the students decide, everyone decides”* (Ant_ET-3_00.41.34). For example, the students decide on the themes of the work projects. The students are responsible for deciding what they want to learn, and what they want to do. On the other hand, the work of teachers is aimed at accompanying and developing the decisions made by the students, ensuring that they learn the knowledge required by the curriculum.

As mentioned above, the **families** also collaborate in the school by participating in various ways, such as providing complementary documentation, testimonies, and/or experiences for the work projects proposed by their children. They point out that the community has always participated, both family members as well as others who have provided personal accounts or contributions to the work projects.

School Didactics and the Teaching profession

By generating knowledge through the development of work projects chosen by students, and because these work projects are flexible, the **methodology** of Antzuola Herri Eskola does not follow a pre-established teaching programme. In another clear attempt to place the students at the centre of activity, they ask the following questions: What do you think? What do they feel? How do you see the world? These questions are the driving force when choosing themes for the work projects. The students choose the work projects through a

democratic process in which they propose different ideas and project themes. Afterwards, they give more detail and visualise the possible learning outcomes that each project might offer. In order to do this, they gather a variety of information on the subject and present their proposals and ideas to their schoolmates in the group or class. Various attempts are made to organise the topics into groups after the themes are established, thus reducing the number of topics and at the same time allowing for complementarity. Finally, once the different proposals have been presented and grouped together, the final choices are made.

During this learning process, *“We don’t place the students in situations of being right or wrong. We use complex situations where there is freedom of opinion, and where the fear of giving a wrong answer, or not knowing the answer, is avoided”* (ET_Ant_dok-3_10). This idea compelled the staff to see the child in a different light, and to do so, they had to reconsider **their true role as teachers**. Thus, they were challenged to cogitate and deepen their vision of education, and think about how to achieve the goals they were pursuing. As a result, they became aware of the importance of their body language, and also of the language used when relating to children, an example of which can be found in the decision to replace the question, “What is it like?”, with a more creative and inclusive question such as, “What do you think?” *“Breaking this dynamic was difficult. We thought, well, we don’t have to ask them how they do this, or how they do that... For us, this was quite a revolution. So if things aren’t right or wrong, how do we deal with this? Then we worked a lot on language, such as how to ask questions of the students; ‘How do you think this should be done?’ Or ‘What do you think about this?’ And so on”* (Ant_ET-2_00.30.56).

By questioning in this way, you provide the opportunity for the students to present a wide variety of perspectives and invite them to share their opinions. This way of asking

questions encourages inquiry, curiosity, and as a result, creativity without the fear of making mistakes. Moreover, during this learning process carried out by students, the teaching staff analyse every project created by each member of the group, both *“from an academic point of view, but also by evaluating many other aspects, such as whether they have only slightly delved into the topic, if they have been afraid of expressing their ideas, and what path they have taken to obtain their own answers...”* (Ant_ET- 2_00.56.31).

When a work project is finished, the students explain what they have learned to different audiences, such as their families, the community, and students from other groups. To do so, they not only present the results of the work projects, but they also make multiple presentations in which they give an account of the tasks carried out, the lessons learned, the difficulties overcome, and the solutions they experienced along the way.

Transformation of the roles of student and teacher

This methodology has also resulted in an evident change in the roles of the different groups involved. In the case of students, they are the starting point of this didactic process. They are the ones who make the decisions and are the protagonists of their own learning. Furthermore, they point out that the aim is the personal success of the students, and the teachers feel that when their school days end, the students do not feel weary of the educational system.

In the case of teachers, *“The idea that the teacher knows everything is abandoned from the beginning.... no, no. What I mean is, we feel safe in saying, ‘I don’t know, but we can all look for the answer together’”* (Ant_ET-2_00.46.12 in a way). Another striking feature of the system is the use of the word “partner”, “companion”, or “guide” to define the role of the teaching staff: “the staff learn together with the students, exploring with them and helping them find the way to fulfil their goals” (Ant_ET-2_00.47.34).

Therefore, the tutor has to interpret, analyse and restructure the group's activities as they evolve, and as new points of interest arise within the work projects. It has also been pointed out that the teachers must possess didactic and pedagogical strategies to face different situations. Moreover, *"They must be able to demonstrate coherence between their ideas and their attitudes"* (Ant_ET-2_00.59.48).

When addressing the subject of participation, *"If the educator sees her or himself merely as a person who gives instructions, what difference is there in 'applying' a closed curriculum – prescribed by administration – and 'applying' a project chosen 'prescriptively' by the students?"* (Ant_dok-2_8).

Pedagogical training

Finally, the staff point out that training is of great importance in achieving a change in the educational paradigm. Immersing oneself in a process of pedagogical innovation means rebuilding the knowledge acquired in the traditional model, and a change of perspective is essential. Therefore, the commitment to improvement and training is considered a task within their role as teachers. In other words, they point out that life-long learning throughout their professional careers is an inherent part of the teaching profession.

Discussion

Both the didactic practice of Antzuola Herri Eskola and its educational organisation include democratic and participatory procedures that promote an inclusive school where harmonious coexistence with others in a more democratic and egalitarian way seems possible. In the process of gathering information, as well as in the categorisation itself, we have been able to observe that in the discourse of the professionals at Antzuola Herri

Eskola, these values are internalised in such a way that it is difficult for them to see education in any other way. In this sense, when we speak of educational innovation, we cannot forget the need to integrate the values upon which the project of the school is built. As pointed out by Escudero et al. (2013), “actions are important, but they must be well-protected with mentalities, beliefs and values, without which they would lack meaning and purpose” (p. 218).

While examining the Educational Project at Antzuola Herri Eskola, we have observed a deep-rooted sense of belonging to an educational community, which in turn reflects a clear concern for the well-being of the people involved. The genuineness of this situation undoubtedly encourages and gives value to the participation and active involvement of the people who make up the community (Gil et al., 1996; Hernández-Prados et al., 2018).

Though it is true that the compulsory education system is in need of transformation and pedagogical innovation, today we can find educational benchmarks, school management models, and didactic practices in which one can reflect and learn in an attempt to achieve a more democratic school. To do so, not only is it necessary to transform the school curriculum, but we must also be willing to transform the school organisation itself into one that confronts structures, practices, and concepts of learning characteristic of other times and other social difficulties.

This study has presented the pedagogical innovation carried out over the course of several decades at a public nursery and primary school in the Basque Country, and continues to be carried out today, which is an uninterrupted endeavour in pedagogical innovation that has lasted for more than 40 years, and in which we find characteristics in common with the educational centres identified by Fielding and Moss (2011), as well as Grosvenor and Pataki (2017).

In summary, for these reasons we want to remind the reader of what the people involved in this project have shown us, or in other words, the main features and components they have used in achieving a more democratic educational programme – an education for the so-called knowledge society:

- Integrate the diversity of the student body in order to create an environment of well-being, cooperation, motivation and freedom of thought where no one feels emotionally threatened, and where the acquisition of knowledge is experienced as something positive that emerges in connection with people, their interactions, interests, concerns, and desire for knowledge (Antzuola, 2004a). For this reason, the relationships formed between the people who make up school communities are particularly important. These interactions should be cordial, respectful and empathetic. Antzuola Herri Eskola is an educational community that strives to guarantee the prosperity, as well as the intellectual and social growth of the people involved, in a welcoming and respectful environment. This school is envisioned as a social framework in which sincere people interact through their own particular way of understanding the world, feeling, and relating to each other, and in which learning is the result of a collective experience of shared well-being. What seems to emerge from this interaction and communication is polyhedral knowledge that allows for cohesive learning experiences, creates bonds, and builds a sense of community that is inclusive and oriented toward the acquisition of knowledge.
- The methodology was developed by the teaching team, and it promotes learning based on dialogue with students and among students in an attempt to overcome the dependence on conceptual content (Gimeno, 1991; Imbernón, 2007; Perrenoud, 2004, 2012). In the words of Freire (1997), teachers do not stop teaching, but they can be questioned, and they no longer possess the absolute truth. This is why the

school emphasises the importance of student participation, and as stated by Freinet (1972), they are aware that no one likes to be bossed around or obliged to carry out tasks that have no objective. With regard to this issue, a child is no different from an adult, and even if the work itself is not necessarily displeasing to him or her, it is the obligation that can paralyse the child. For this reason, students must be heard in all decision-making processes. A democratic school should allow students to decide how, and in what areas, they will be assessed. Freinet (1982) points out that by changing work techniques, the conditions of school life are modified, a new atmosphere is generated, and relations between children and the environment, as well as between students and teachers (including family members), are improved. Moreover, this is perhaps the most effective help that can be offered to compulsory education today.

- The teacher becomes a knowledge mediator– the person who poses the problem and ceases to be the one who teaches. Instead, she or he becomes the person who organizes knowledge and learning (Gadotti, 2007). At Antzuola Herri Eskola, the teaching staff represent one authority, yet this authority reflects and makes decisions to ensure that this small microcosm of society composed of a group of students becomes a true cultural community, and that these children are the real driving force of the educational community. This teaching authority acts as a bridge between the problems that students must face and those that humanity has had to face throughout its history, hence its didactic choice in favour of work projects. This methodology produces knowledge from the students' own experiences without being influenced by previously developed didactic programming prescribed by teachers. Seeing the students as active participants with the capability of making decisions about their future frees teachers from having to decide continuously for them, while offering

collective options for deciding together on the steps to be taken. This provides the opportunity to promote awareness of the diversity of thoughts, ideas, achievements and circumstances that arise in the daily life of this educational community. This type of teaching raises the question of what is the best framework for allowing all children to be involved and experience their feelings, as well as how close this type of teaching is to those feelings in order for this process to allow such sentiments to be perceived as elements to take into account, as well as to help regulate and guide the process, both from a collective and individual point of view. This teaching endeavour seeks to give people access to knowledge, well-being and culture. The evolution of the teaching role seems to have its roots in the notion of democratic schools (Apple & Beane, 1997; Bambozzi et al, 2020; Thoilliez, 2019), where learning for life requires a creative curriculum in the search for answers to the problems that humanity has faced throughout its history. This learning process uses imagination to respond to and overcome these problems and to reflect on these processes collectively.

- There is a need for a holistic view of the school curriculum that integrates knowledge from different subjects in a flexible, local and interdisciplinary way. It is no surprise that since the 1970s, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 1970, 1973) has made significant efforts in defence of interdisciplinarity as a valid resource in the resolution of social problems and challenges (Karrera et al., 2014). If one wants to adapt a school's organization to the needs of this emerging curriculum, one must be aware that the space for learning is not located in the classroom, but in its surroundings, in the community, the town, the city or region. In short, right next to our schools. This compels us to rethink and reorganize spaces and groups both inside and outside the school.

- Consideration must also be given to all of the participants who want to take part in the process of pedagogical innovation of a school. To make this possible, it seems to be imperative to question the figure of the leader who decides and is responsible for the actions of the centre. In general, the active involvement of the administrative team is fundamental, and as stressed by Murillo (2006), the directors are the ones who must take the first step toward change. There is a type of leadership that takes into account the community and leads democratically, which is known as distributed leadership (Bolívar, 2000; 2010; López & Lavié, 2010; Murillo, 2006). Distributed leadership is a new conceptual framework for analysing and addressing school leadership. It involves much more than a simple redesign of tasks. It implies a change of culture, which involves the commitment and involvement of all members of the school community in the running, operation and management of a school. In this way, distributed leadership benefits from the skills of others for a common cause, so that leadership is manifested at all levels (Harris and Chapman, 2002). This profound rethinking of the role of leadership harnesses the skills of the members of the educational community with regard to a collective mission. In turn, this action is in line with the ideas of democracy and community participation, and everything these concepts entail— a school that is more equitable, participatory, and ultimately, more democratic.

As we have previously stated, the way of relating to students and perceiving knowledge are some of the fundamental keys of change towards a more democratic and inclusive school. The power relations that exist today leave students in a vulnerable position. If schools continue to maintain this point of view, and if students continue to be seen as a group without the necessary capability of deciding and taking charge of their

own learning, and therefore of their own lives, then the participation that we demand and want to promote will not become a reality.

Considering possible lines of research in the future initiated by the ALHE team (*UPV/EHU*), we believe one of the priorities must be to focus on the aspects mentioned above in order to examine in more detail the truly active participation of students, how to implement such a participative process, and what practices might encourage participation. In this sense, we consider that students' voices are also very important, and in order to break that silence, we have held 28 focus groups with the generations that have studied at Antzuola since this project began. We hope we will have relevant information and results to publish soon.

Moreover, we believe that the first step in becoming immersed in an innovative educational process is training and reflection, aspects to which Antzuola Herri Eskola has dedicated a great deal of time. For this reason, we want to continue to support, promote and disseminate benchmark practices in schools and educational centres that carry out research based on participatory processes of reflection and pedagogical criticism, similar to that of Antzuola Herri Eskola. This will provide a deeper understanding of the school itself, and thereby assist in defining guidelines for change.

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